

FACTORS AFFECTING THE QUALITY OF BUDGET REALIZATION REPORTS AT PARTNERS IN THE SERVICES OFFICE OF THE STATE BUDGET

ABDUL ROHMAN¹, IWAN EFRIANDY², CHRISTIAN DAMAR SAGARA SITEPU³,
ANTON INDRA BUDIMAN⁴, ABDULLAH⁵ and ABDUL BASHIR*⁶

^{1, 2, 3, 4, 5} Department of Accounting, Universitas Sriwijaya, South Sumatra, Indonesia.

⁶ Department of Development Economics, Universitas Sriwijaya, South Sumatra, Indonesia.

*Corresponding author E-mail: abd.bashir@unsri.ac.id

Abstract

This study investigates the factors that influence the quality of budget realization reports to partners in the State Treasury Service at the Palembang City representative office. These factors include human resource competence; utilization of information technology; data reconciliation; and financial reporting application. The data for this study is primary with a sample of 60 informants in the finance section of the State Treasury Service representative office in Palembang City. This study method uses a multiple linear regression model. Our findings show that the use of information technology, data reconciliation, and financial reporting applications have a positive and significant impact on the quality of budget realization reports. Meanwhile, the competence of human resources has no significant effect on the quality of budget realization reports.

Keywords: Competency; Information technology; Reconciliation; Financial reporting application; Quality report

INTRODUCTION

The Agency Accounting System (SAI) and the General Accounting System (SAU) have different data centers even though the source documents that compose the data are the same. In the process of inputting data, visual errors or human errors (Shryane et al., 1998). The impact of this error is the occurrence of dissimilarity in state financial administration data between SAI and SAU which results in invalid and accountable reports (Korol, 2019; Yan, 2012; Sneed, 2007; Samosir & Setiyawati., 2019). Therefore, this reconciliation process is needed. Even though the law on state finances has been produced for a long time, there are still problems that occur during the minus ceiling reconciliation process (Gamage, 2010; Elson, 2004). There is still a difference or remaining between the budget ceiling and its realization (Setyawan & Gamayuni, 2020).

We identify from the budget realization data for 2016-2020 that was published by the Directorate General of Treasury, Ministry of Finance, to be precise at Services Office of the State Budget, the budget ceiling given by the government to the work unit in 2016 was IDR.675,708,580,000, while the realization of the ceiling absorbed by the work unit is IDR.700,157,013,004, there is a difference of IDR.24,448,433,004. Then for 2017, the budget ceiling is IDR.85,051,750,000, but the realization is IDR.91,167,584,969, and there is a difference of IDR.6,115,834,969. Furthermore, in 2018, the budget ceiling is IDR.325,546,046,000, but the realization is IDR.349,151,766,883, there is a difference of

IDR.23,605,720,883. Then in 2019, the budget ceiling is IDR.186,852,584,000, but the realization is IDR.195,666,557,416 there is a difference of IDR.8,813,973,416. Furthermore, in 2020, the budget ceiling is IDR.14,787,810,000, but the realization of the ceiling absorbed by the work unit is IDR.14,806,687,994, and there is a difference of IDR.24,472,994. We assume that this is a human and visual error resulting in an invalid and accountable report. Even though there is currently a reconciliation process, there are still discrepancies between the budget ceiling and its realization.

At the beginning of each month no later than seven working days after the month ends, the work unit is obliged to carry out reconciliation at the Services Office of the State Budget. This reconciliation is carried out to see if there is a match between the SAI data managed by the work unit and the SAU data managed by the Services Office of the State Budget as the proxy of the state general treasurer. This data will be the initial work on the Central Government's Budget Realization Report and Balance Sheet. This study is very important to do because the implementation of the spending budget ceiling realization from 2016-2020 still has many discrepancies, the value of which is quite large. This is very important for the work unit to find out why there is such a large discrepancy. Many factors cause this large difference. For this reason, we tried to examine the effect of human resource competence, utilization of information technology, data reconciliation, and financial reporting applications on the quality of budget realization reports for partners at the Services Office of the State Budget.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Agency Theory

Theory that describes the existence of a relationship in the form of a contractual relationship between parties in a company. Jensen & Meckling (1976) states that this agency relationship will occur when one or several parties (principal) send another party (agent) to perform services/services, where principal will delegate his authority to the agent for decision making. Agency theory describes the behavior of parties within the company, namely between principals and agents (Glinkowska & Kaczmarek, 2015; Bonazzi & Islam, 2007). Where in this theory, shareholders act as principals, while managers act as agents. Shareholders as principals will delegate their powers to the company manager as agents. With the existence of an agency relationship between the two parties, there will be a tendency for problems to arise which are commonly known as conflicts of interest. The background to the emergence of this problem is due to the existence of two parties in the company, namely managers and shareholders who have differences in achieving their respective goals.

Shareholders as principals certainly want returns and in the shortest time for what has been invested. different with company managers as agents who actually expect to be able to receive rewards in large numbers in accordance with what they have done in achieving company goals, these rewards can be in the form of compensation or incentives. Shareholders instruct managers (agents) to be able to control the company so that the company can display good performance as desired by the shareholders. In managing the company, managers are required to convey

performance and internal information related to the company to shareholders (Rezvani et al., 2016; Du & Yu, 2021).

This is done because it is the manager who understands the actual situation of the company and the manager who has direct involvement with company information. Therefore, it can be ascertained that the knowledge possessed by managers regarding the company is wider than that of shareholders. This condition is known as information asymmetry. It is this information asymmetry that causes managers to tend to take, namely opportunistic behavior actions aimed at promoting their own individual interests (Wiryadi & Sebrina, 2013; Barus & Setawati, 2015; Tsvetkov, 2014; Cho et al., 2013).

Agency theory, everyone is considered to be trying to prioritize his personal welfare. For example, managers who act as agents who are motivated to take opportunistic for their own welfare. actions opportunistic taken by managers in managing the company are by increasing company profits so that they can get a fee for what they have done (Jensen & Meckling, 1976). Managers also often act inconsistently with what the shareholders want, namely by not disclosing information properly, this is done solely for profit. It is this difference in interests held by the principal and agent that can later lead to the non-compliance of managers and cause differences in the process of reconciling the budget realization report.

Competency of Human Resources

Human resources are one of the most important organizational elements, because human resources play a role as the main supporting pillar as well as driving wheels of the organization in an effort to realize the vision and mission and goals of the organization. According to Stone et al. (2020); and Decenzo & Robbins (2010) the ability of human resources is as an individual capacity to perform various tasks in a particular job. Therefore, an entity must manage human resources as well as possible so that they can contribute optimally in achieving organizational goals.

In managing state finances, the government should have adequate human resource competencies, which are supported by the knowledge, skills and attitudes required in carrying out their duties (Swanda & Suryana, 2020; Siahaan et al., 2016). So that to implement a government financial accounting system, human resources with this capacity will be able to understand the logic in the government financial accounting system, so that it can produce output in the form of financial reports that are in accordance with government accounting standards and will also produce outcomes in the form of reliable financial information that is not misleading for stakeholders (Stubbs, & Higgins, 2018; Ball, 2006).

Individual quality can be optimal if the individual has reliable competence in their field. The reliability of human resource competencies can be formed, where the formation is heavily influenced by the organization's ability to manage human resources into several individual competency specifications, According to Alsaadat (2019) including: (1) goal achievement competencies, (2) problem solving competencies, (3) interaction competencies with peers, and (4) teamwork. Thus, the synergy of the competencies of each individual jointly optimizes performance overall. State apparatus which constitutes government human resources,

professionals are not only required to have expertise capacity, high moral responsibility but also to serve the community, and have and be able to integrate within themselves the technical skills needed to carry out their work (Ngang et al., 2015; McNamara, 2013; Brinkerhoff, 2006).

H₁: Competence of human resources affects the quality of budget realization reports to partners at the State Treasury Service Office

Utilization of Information Technology

Currently, the use of information technology has become a basic requirement that can be relied upon in carrying out daily tasks optimally, accurately and precisely time. Utilization of information technology is the optimal use of computers, software, and others of the same kind. Information technology includes computers (mainframe, mini, micro), software, databases, internet networks, electronic commerce, and other types related to technology (Shah et al., 2017; Harris et al., 2000).

Some of the benefits of using information technology (Shah et al., 2017; Harris et al., 2000), include processing transactions and other data faster, accuracy in calculations and comparisons is greater, processing each transaction is lower, preparing reports and other outputs is timelier, place more compact data storage with greater accessibility when needed, wider data entry options and provision of output and higher productivity for employees and managers who learn to use computers effectively in routine responsibilities and decision making.

The government through Government Regulation no. 56 of 2005 concerning information systems participating in utilizing information technology in achieving the vision and mission of the organization. The law explains that in order to follow up on the implementation of a development process that is in line with the principles of good governance, the Central Government and Regional Governments are obliged to develop and utilize advances in information technology to increase the ability to manage finances, and distribute financial information. to public service.

H₂: Utilization of Technology affect the quality of budget realization reports to partners in the State Treasury Service Office

Data Reconciliation

Reconciliation is one of the keys in the effort to prepare accountable financial reports. This is due to its quite important role in minimizing the occurrence of differences in recording which have an impact on the validity and accuracy of the data presented in the financial statements. In order for the accounting data produced by the central government accounting system to be reliable, it is necessary to carry out reconciliation to ensure the accuracy and accuracy of recording accounting data as mandated in article 33 of Government Regulation Number 8 of 2006 concerning Financial Reporting and Performance of Government Agencies.

H₃: Data Reconciliation, affecting the quality of budget realization reports to partners at the State Treasury Service Office

Financial Reporting Applications

From 2004 to 2008 Audit Board of the Republic of Indonesia (BPK) opinion on Goods and Services Procurement Policy Institute (LKPP) was a disclaimer (not giving an opinion). In 2009 LKPP then obtained the title of Fair With Exceptions (WDP) until 2015. There were 6 problems that caused the exceptions in the 2015 LKPP, 2 of the six problems could only be resolved by periodic reconciliation of financial transactions between work units and State Treasury Service Office and analysis/review of financial reports prepared by work units from the lowest level to the top. The Directorate General of Treasury then launched a web-based reconciliation application called the financial reporting applications. Financial reports application, which stands for electronic reconciliation and financial reports, is a web-based application developed for the purpose of reconciling financial transaction data and preparing financial reports for state ministries/agencies. After the launch of this application, in 2016 for the first time LKPP received an Unqualified Opinion (WTP) since 12 years LKPP was first compiled and audited. The financial reports application has a large role as evidenced by the achievement of LKPP Unqualified opinion (WTP) in 2016.

The financial reports application is used to consolidate data for all Work Units and for reconciliation between Work Units and State Treasury Service Office. The financial reports web-based application facilitates the reconciliation process where financial statement reconciliation is only at one level, namely the lowest level between the work unit and the State Treasury Service Office which is carried out on all financial transaction data to fulfill the principles of effectiveness and efficiency, as well as accountability and transparency in financial reporting, without reducing the reliability of the financial statements themselves. The valid data resulting from the reconciliation is used to prepare regional-level financial reports up to the Ministry/Institution level.

The use of data with a single database in financial reporting applications makes it unnecessary for reconciliation at the regional level to the Ministry/Institution level, although in practice there are still differences in data between the Agency Accounting System (SAI) and the Central Accounting System (SiAP). The Agency Accounting System (SAI) and the Central Accounting System (SiAP) have different data centers even though the source documents that compose the data are the same. So that if the data is used to compile financial reports, the resulting report will be invalid and accountable.

H4: Financial reporting applications affect the quality of budget realization reports to partners at the State Treasury Service Office.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The research method is a scientific way to obtain data with specific purposes and uses. The data source for this study is primary data obtained through an interview process with selected sources in charge of government finance. The instrument used was a questionnaire consisting of core questions answered by respondents with a Likert scale of 1-5 (ordinal data). A valid sample was

obtained by 60 respondents. This study was conducted in January-August 2022 located at the state treasury office. The description of the data and variables is presented in Table 1 as follows:

Table 1: Research data and definition of variables

Variables	Definition	Scala
Quality of Budget Realization Report (Y)	Normative measures that must be implemented in accounting information so that it can fulfill the objectives to be achieved, namely relevant, reliable, comparable and understandable (PP No 71 tahun 2010)	Interval
Human Resource Competency (X1)	The basic characteristics of a person consisting of knowledge, skills and attitudes that have a causal relationship with extraordinary work performance or work effectiveness (Spencer, 2008)	Interval
Utilization of Information Technology (X2)	Utilization of information technology is the optimal use of computers, software/software, and others of the same kind. Information technology includes computers, software, databases, networks, electronic commerce, and other types related to technology (Harris et al., 2000)	Interval
Data Reconciliation (X3)	Data reconciliation is the process of matching financial transaction data processed with several different systems/sub-systems based on the same source document. (PMK RI Nomor 210/PMK.05/2013)	Interval
Financial Report Application (X4)	The application for financial reports is used to consolidate data for all work units and for reconciliation between work units and data from the State Treasury Service Office	Interval

The data analysis method used in this study is a quantitative method by applying a multiple linear regression model. This method is to identify the influence of human resource competence, information technology utilization, data reconciliation, and financial reporting applications on the quality of budget realization reports for business partners in the State Treasury Service Office.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Characteristics of respondents based on gender, education, course/training n field finance, and based on tenure working period at State Treasury Service Office and work units throughout South Sumatra can be seen in the Table 2 as follows:

Table 2: Frequency Distribution of Respondent Characteristics

Variables	Characteristics	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	50.00
	Famale	50.00
Education	Senior high school	20,00
	Diploma	18.30
	Bachelor's degree	61.70
	Postgraduate	0,00
Course/Training n Field Finance	Never	6.70
	(1-2 times)	30.00
	(3-5 times)	50.00
	(6-10 times)	6.70
	(11-20 times)	6.70
Based on Tenure Working Period	< 5 Years	21.70
	5- 10 Years	20.00
	>10 Years	58.30

Source: Authors calculation

Result of validity test of item statement for variables

Testing the validity of the instrument using SPSS software, the validity value can be seen in the corrected item-total correlation column. If the correlation number obtained has an r-test > 0.2542, it can be concluded that the questionnaire items are valid (Sugiyono, 2016). In testing the validity of the research instrument in the form of a questionnaire consisting of 21 statements consisting of 6 statements for the human resource competence variable (X1); 5 statements for the utilization of information technology (X2); 5 statements for the data reconciliation (X3); 5 statements for the financial report appplication (X4); and 5 statements for the quality of budget realization reports (Y), before testing the validity of the data obtained, both variable X and Y are tabulated in advance in calculating the scores on the questionnaire results to facilitate calculations using Microsoft Excel.

Table 3 reports the results data processing through the SPSS program show that the variable of X1; X2; X3; X4; and Y obtains an r-test greater than r-critical, it shows that all variable of the X1; X2; X3; X4; and Y statement items that have been submitted in this research instrument are declared to have met the requirements (valid).

Table 3: Validity test of item statement for variables

Human Resources Competency (X1)			
Item Statement	r-test	r-critical	Description
X1.1	0.569	0.2542	Valid
X1.2	0.715	0.2542	Valid
X1.3	0.550	0.2542	Valid
X1.4	0.524	0.2542	Valid
X1.5	0.439	0.2542	Valid
X1.6	0.348	0.2542	Valid

Table 3: Validity test of item statement for variables (continued)

Information Technology Utilization (X2)			
Item Statement	R-test	Rcritical	Information
X2.1	0.522	0.2542	Valid
X2.2	0.643	0.2542	Valid
X2.3	0.772	0.2542	Valid
X2.4	0.705	0.2542	Valid
X2 .5	0.745	0.2542	Valid
Data Reconciliation (X3)			
Item Statement	R-test	Rcritical	Description
X3.1	0.735	0.2542	Valid
X3.2	0.672	0.2542	Valid
X3.3	0.634	0.2542	Valid
X3.4	0.541	0.2542	Valid
X3.5	0.654	0.2542	Valid
Financial Report Applications (X4)			
Item Statement	Rcount	Rcritical	Description
X4.1	0.715	0.2542	Valid
X4.2	0.665	0.2542	Valid
X4.3	0.632	0.2542	Valid
X4.4	0.587	0, 2542	Valid
X4.5	0.624	0.2542	Valid
Quality of Budget Realization Reports (Y)			
Statement Items	Rcount	Rcritical	Description
Y1	0.616	0.2542	Valid
Y2	0.709	0.2542	Valid
Y3	0.692	0.2542	Valid
Y4	0.650	0.2542	Valid
Y5	0.691	0.2542	Valid

Source: Authors calculation

Result of reliability test of variables

After the validity test research is carried out, the reliability test will be carried out. According to Singh (2017) and Cook & Beckman (2006) the reliability test is used to determine the level of consistency of measuring instruments, whether the measuring instruments used are reliable when used many times will potentially produce the same data (Reliable). The following shows the results of the data reliability test for each research variable in Table 4 as follows:

Table 4: Reliability test of variables

Variables	Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
X1	0.696	6
X2	0.768	5
X3	0.757	5
X4	0.734	5
Y	0.767	5

Source: Authors calculation

Reliability testing of research instruments analysis method cronbach's alpha. To determine whether the research instrument is declared variable, namely by comparing Cronbach's alpha with an alpha of 0.60, if Cronbach's alpha greater than 0.60 it can be said that the instrument used is reliable (Singh, 2017; and Cook & Beckman, 2006). Based on the results of data processing using the SPSS, it can be concluded that all the variables used for this study are reliable and can be continued for further testing.

Result of Normality test

The normality test in this study was conducted with the aim of testing whether in a regression model there are confounding or residual variables that have a normal distribution. In the normality test in this study using the Kolmogorov Smirnov for normality test. The result show that if the probability value is > 0.05 , it can be concluded that the data is normally distributed. Table 10 reports the number of Asymp. Sig. (2.tailed) is greater than 0.05, which is 0.278. So that the data in this study are normally distributed.

Table 5: Normality test using Kolmogorov-Smirnov

		Unstandardized Residual
N	Sample	60
Normal Parameters ^a	Mean	0.000
	Std. Deviation	0.953
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	0.128
	Positive	0.071
	Negative	-0.128
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		0.992
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed).		0.278

Source: Authors calculation

Result of Heteroscedasticity test

Test The heteroscedasticity test aims to see whether in the regression model there is an inequality of the confounding variable from one observation to another. If variance from the residual of one observation to another observation remains, then it is called homoscedasticity and if it is different it is called heteroscedasticity.

Figure 2: Results of Heteroscedasticity test with Scatterplot

Source: Authors calculation

Figure 2 reports the dots spread randomly and do not form a pattern, either above or below the number 0 on the Y axis, this means not heteroscedasticity occurs in the regression model. This concluded that this research instrument meets the assumption of heteroscedasticity.

Result of Multicollinearity

Test The multicollinearity test in this study was conducted with the aim of knowing whether or not there is a correlation between the independent variables (X). This is important because one of the conditions for a good regression model is that there is no multicollinearity. If the VIF value is less than 10 and the tolerance value is not less than 0.10, it can be concluded that multicollinearity does not occur (Gujarati, 2021).

Table 6: Multicollinearity test

Model	Collinearity Statistics	
	Tolerance	VIF
Human Resource Competency (X1)	0.697	1.436
Technology Information Utilization (X2)	0.522	1.914
Data Reconsiliation (X3)	0.634	1.578
Financial Report Application (X4)	0.534	1.378

Source: Authors calculation

Based on the SPSS output data for the multicollinearity test, it can be seen from Table 6 show that the VIF value which shows that none of the independent variables has a VIF value of more

than 10. Furthermore, the tolerance shows the same thing, no variable has a value smaller than 0.10. So it can be concluded that there is no serious multicollinearity between the independent variables in the regression model in this study.

Result of Multiple Linear Regression

This study to investigate how much influence the independent variable such as human resource competence, utilization of information technology, data reconciliation, and financial report application on dependent variable is quality of budget realization reports. Table 7 report the estimation result of multiple linear regression equation as follows:

Table 7: Multiple Linear Regression

Dependent variable: Quality of Budget Realization Reports (Y)				
Variables	Coefficients	Std. Error	t-stat	Prob.
Constant	1.816	2.562	0.709	0.481
Human Resource Competency (X1)	0.085	0.096	0.879	0.383
Technology Information Utilization (X2)	0.247	0.116	2.128	0.038
Data Reconsiliation (X3)	0.585	0.115	5.085	0.000
Financial Report Application (X4)	0.385	0.105	4.085	0.000
Summary: F-stat: 23.449 (0.000); Adjusted R ² : 0.5720				

Source: Authors calculation

Table 7 show that the determination coefficient of adjusted R² is 0.5720 or 57.20 percent. This implies that variations in human resource competency variables, information technology utilization, data reconciliation, and financial reporting applications be able to explain variations in the quality of budget realization reports by 57.20 percent, while the remaining 42.80 percent is explained by other variables outside this research model. The F-stat of 23,449 indicates that the null hypothesis is rejected, this implies that the independent variable jointly has an influence on the dependent variable. The constant coefficient of 1.816, this implies that the quality of the current budget realization report will increase is 1.816 assuming that the human resource competence variable, information technology utilization, data reconciliation, and financial report application variable are currently in a constant state or fixed.

The human resource competency insignificant effect on the quality of budget realization reports, which means the null hypothesis is accepted. This implies that an increase in human resource competency not noticeably improve the quality of budget realization reports assuming ceteris paribus. The results of this study are in line with research by Sumaryati et al. (2017), showing that the human resource competency has no significance effect. This means that the competence of human resources has no significant effect on the quality of the budget realization report. This is due to the condition of the level of education of employees who are not in accordance with their fields, so that employees cannot quickly understand what needs to be done. The low level of employee understanding of tasks regarding financial reports and their functions as well as obstacles in data processing can also have an impact on delays in

completing tasks that must be completed. One of them is the presentation of financial statements.

The information technology utilization has positive sign and significant effect on the quality of budget realization reports, which means the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that an increase in the utilization of information technology by 1 percent will increase the quality of budget realization reports by 0.247 percent assuming *ceteris paribus*. This means that the higher the utilization of information technology in the work unit, the better the quality of the budget realization report by obtaining the reliability of operating results and the ability to reduce human error. The results of this study are in line with the results of research conducted by Budiono et al. (2018); Akhmad et al. (2017); and Erawati (2018) who found that the information technology utilization variable has a significant and positive influence on the quality of budget realization reports.

The data reconciliation has a positive sign and significant influence on the quality of budget realization reports, which means the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that an increase in data reconciliation of 1 percent will increase the quality of budget realization reports by 0.585 percent assuming *ceteris paribus*. This indicates that there is a positive correlation between data reconciliation on the quality of budget realization reports. That is, the higher the data reconciliation, the higher the quality of the budget realization report. The logical consequence can be stated that the role of data reconciliation is very important to minimize the occurrence of differences in recording due to not being timely which has an impact on the validity and accuracy of the data presented in the financial statements. For the data generated by the central government accounting system to be relevant and reliable, it is necessary to carry out data reconciliation to ensure the accuracy and accuracy of recording accounting data. This is supported by Suryaningsih & Sulthon Limbong (2016); Oflagi et al. (2018) which shows that simultaneous and partial data reconciliation affects the quality of financial reports. Herdianto's research (2015) also shows that reconciliation has proven to have a positive effect on the quality of the financial reports of work units at the Ministry of Manpower in the DKI Jakarta area and UPTP work units in the regions.

The financial report application has a positive sign and has a significant influence on the quality of the budget realization report, which means the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that an increase in the Financial Report Application by 1 percent will increase the quality of the budget realization report by 0.343 percent assuming *ceteris paribus*. This indicates that there is a positive correlation between the financial report applications on the quality of budget realization reports. That is, the higher the financial report application, the higher the quality of the budget realization report. The logical consequence can be stated that the role of the E-Rekon and LK application is very important in order to minimize the occurrence of differences in recording due to not being timely which has an impact on the validity and accuracy of the data presented in the financial reports. In order for the data generated by the central government accounting system to be relevant and reliable, it is necessary to apply financial report application to ensure the accuracy and accuracy of recording accounting data. This is supported by the research of Oflagi et al. (2018) which shows that simultaneously the financial report

application provides a breakthrough in reconciliation and consolidation of ministry/agency level financial reports. Reconciliation can be done from the satker office. Data integrity is also getting better because there are no more data differences between the satker accounting unit and the accounting unit above it or data differences between the satker and the State Treasury Service Office can be resolved more quickly.

CONCLUSIONS

In our study concluded that the use of information technology, data reconciliation, and financial reporting applications have a positive and significant impact on the quality of budget realization reports. While the competence of human resources has no significant effect on the quality of the budget realization report. The implication of this study recommends for work units throughout South Sumatra to improve the quality of financial reports need continue to participate in socialization, technical guidance (capacity building) and training both held by the Ministry of Finance and from the work unit itself, so that the competence of human resources, utilization of information technology, and data reconciliation is getting better. And, even more ideally, work units throughout South Sumatra place human resources with appropriate qualifications or an educational background in accounting as preparers of financial reports. This is necessary so that the preparers of financial reports have high competence in preparing financial reports. It is hoped that the next researcher, if he wants to take the same topic as the author, will broaden the scope of the research by adding research samples, research variables and indicators that are different from this research.

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